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The optimization of process parameters of three-dimensional needled composites based on ANN and GA

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Application and technology of needled composites

Application

Question: The needled process parameters are numerous, so how to find the best process parameters?

A surrogate model for optimizing process parameters

BP neural network diagram

Optimal individual preservation strategy of genetic algorithm diagram

Optimization results

$$f(\text{fitness}) = 0.25 E_1 + 0.25 E_3 + 0.25 G_{12} + 0.25 G_{23}$$

Genetic algorithm fitness changes with genetic algebra

Stiffness properties of materials before and after optimization

Stiffness properties	No optimization results(GPa)	Optimization results(GPa)
E1	57.51	64.1120
E3	30.92	45.8
G12	14.09	14.38
G23	9.856	9.560
fitness	28.31	33.46

Process parameters of the optimized material

Material parameters	Needling depth(mm)	Needling density(needle/cm ²)	Needle way x(mm)	Needle way y(mm)
Results	8.459	13.93	1.015	1.693